

*Climate and cultural based design and
market valuable technology solutions for Plus Energy Houses*

Local policies and boundary conditions for PEHs

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List of acronyms

BBSR	Federal Institute for Building, Urban and Spatial Research (Germany)
CHP	Combined heat and power plant
CO ₂	CO ₂ -equivalent or greenhouse gas emissions (GWP)
Coll.	solar thermal collector
CSPE	Contribution to the Public Electricity Service (France)
CTA	transmission tariff contribution (France)
DHW	Domestic hot water
EDF	Electricité De France
EE	Renewable energy
EEG	Law for the expansion of renewable energies (Germany)
EEWärmeG	Renewable Energies Heat Act (Germany), national
e-mobility	electro-mobility
EnEV	Energy Saving Ordinance (Germany)
ep	Primary energy
ERDF	French network manager
EU	European Union
EWärmeG	Renewable Heat Act (Germany, Baden-Wuerttemberg), local
FR	France
GEG 2020	Building Energy Act (Germany)
GER	Germany
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIS	Geografic Information system
GSE	Energy Services Manager (Italy)
GWP	greenhouse gas emissions
HPHC	Peak/Off-Peak tariff option (France)
HT`	Transmission heat loss
IT	Italy
KfW	Reconstruction Loan Corporation (Germany)
kW	Kilowatt
kWh/(m ² y)	kWh per m ² and year

kWp	Kilowatt peak
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
NOK	Norwegian krone (currency)
NOR	Norway
nZEB	nearly zero energy buildings
Pa	Pascal
PEB	Plus Energy Buildings
PV	photovoltaic
Power2Gas	Power to gas
RE	Environmental Regulation (France)
RES	Renewable energy system
RGE	Recognized Guarantor of the Environment
RT	French "thermal regulation"
SFP	Specific fan power
SPF	Seasonal performance factor
Sq	Square
TCFE	tax on the final consumption of electricity (France)
TEK	Regulations on technical requirements for construction works (Norway)
th	thermal
Tic	conventional indoor temperature (France)
TURPE	Tariff for the Use of Public Electricity Networks (France)
TVA	Taxe sur la Valeur Ajoutée (France, see VAT)
VAT	Value Added Tax
WP	workpackage

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1 Executive summary

Residential plus energy buildings (PEB) are highly efficient buildings which cover the building performance and the occupants' energy demand requirements at both, household and building, levels from integrated renewable energy systems (RES). The energy produced onsite by these decentralized RES may exceed the total building energy consumption over a specific period of time. A PEB according to CULTURAL-E has to fulfil the following criteria:

- Positive onsite primary energy balance over the year
- Maximum CO₂ emissions of 2 kgCO₂/(m²y) during building operation phase (building heating, domestic hot water, ventilation, auxiliaries, building cooling, lighting **and user appliances**)
- Limited extra-costs compared to nZEB 2020
- Low environmental and social impacts, as evaluated with a LCA approach and considering wide system boundaries

Each EU country has its own building regulation and criteria for building insulation, efficiency of system technologies and share of renewable energy supply. Going in detail, the regulations differ remarkably and are not comparable:

- Energy demand is either limited to fixed values or variable values using the building reference method
- The regulations assess different outcome units such as 'useful' or 'primary' energy
- None of the four participating countries' climate-relevant GHG emissions are directly regulated within the building codes
- None of the building regulations consider the total onsite energy demand during the complete life cycle - including the demand for users' appliances and the embodied energy for the building construction-, although the boundaries for the assessment of residential buildings have slight differences.
- The legal minimum requirements have strong disparities, hence it implies variations in regard to achievable GWP reductions. Except for Norway (ban on fossil fuels for heat supply and a largely renewable electricity mix) the minimum requirements for nZEB are behind the PEB standard.

Nevertheless, it exists several incentives for promoting PEB using innovative energy concepts beyond the existing minimum legal requirements:

- Remuneration for surplus of PV fed into the public grid.
- Partial VAT reduction for PV systems.

- Various funding programs for efficient building standards, heating systems based on renewable energies, insulation of the building envelope, photovoltaic systems, storage systems or e-mobility.

So far, the existing incentives did not increase the share of PEB significantly. In order to reach PEB standard, a local production of renewable energy is essential. The renewable energy generated by building integrated PV systems can cover a share large part of the electricity required. Depending on the country, there are different climatic, organizational, financial and legal framework conditions that favor or hinder the direct use of the onsite energy produced. The following barriers for PEB could be identified:

- Lack of financial incentives due to legal requirements.
- VAT rates on investments of PV systems which are, in the French context, balanced by specific respective funding schemes for PV systems.
- In the German context, the related costs to the self-consumed electricity, from onsite PV systems, are partially combined, with the costs for: (i) administrative procedures such as measurement-billing and (ii) high levies.
- Widespread of low energy costs for the electricity consumed from the grid (investment payback for PV becomes high).
- No monetary remuneration for providing control energy by demand and generation management in a renewable energy system
- The high investment cost for smart metering still exceeding the cost savings in private households (variable electricity tariffs).
- Deletion of the trade tax exemption for the housing companies, in case they act as an energy supplier.

In addition, the overarching energy infrastructure affects the CO₂ emissions and the primary energy demands of buildings. The boundary conditions in Norway with for a share of the electricity from the grid in Norway, which is generated from hydrogen power plants (18 gCO_{2e} per kWh) in comparison to Germany with a power supply of still 40 % of fossil energy sources (440 gCO_{2e} per kWh) favor the implementation of PEB with less building integrated PV necessary.

Outlook and recommendations

In order to achieve a real steering effect, a fixed CO₂ target value for buildings has to be set instead of maintaining the previous assessment of reference buildings and primary energy requirement. There exists a large number of subsidies' models for efficient building standards, heating systems based on renewable energies, insulation of the building envelope, photovoltaic systems or e-mobility. But not always they are made use of and neither the effectiveness of the measures are transparent in regard to CO₂ savings or they are proven to be enough. Future funding programs should may subsidize

energy concepts for CO₂-saving, such as PEB design criteria instead of individual and isolated measures. Or there may be an obligation to pay taxes when targets according to the 'individual climate protection plans' of the building are not met; or, a subsidisation of monitored CO₂ savings, when they are already achieved beyond the foreseen targets.

The CO₂ emissions' pricing of energy sources across all sectors, including the fossil fuels used for heat and transport, is an effective measure as well. In Germany, there is a starting of CO₂ pricing with 25 € per tonCO₂ by 2021¹. In order to develop a real steering effect in reducing the greenhouse potential and the spread of PEB concepts, the CO₂ costs must be set up to 180 € per tonCO₂, including an increase up to 240 € per tonCO₂ by 2050 (UBA 2013)².

Another objective of PEB design is to reduce the environmental impact in the entire life cycle of a building. Therefore, the boundaries for the building assessment has to be expanded by the proportion of the embodied energy for building construction and the energy requirement for building operation, including the user appliances. A future CO₂ target value for residential buildings must consider these boundaries in order to further expand the use of self-generated electricity from locally generated PV power and thus to support the spread of PEB design concepts. In order to promoting sector coupling of energy demand in building, it is sensible to assess the energy demand of e-mobility in the medium term.

For the envisioned coupling of the electricity, heating and mobility sectors, it is a crucial aspect to consider the introduction of district level approaches compared to an individual assessment of buildings. By implementing energy systems at district level, which includes the generation and storage of renewable energy systems, as well as the provision of local heat and electricity for buildings and mobility, CO₂ savings can be achieved that go beyond the individual building approach. A district level approach also makes other important aspects possible, such as energy storage and flexibility for energy demand and generation, and thus contribute to the grid stabilization. Variable energy pricing could be an incentive to provide control energy to reduce peak loads and make better use of renewable energies.

¹ Klimaschutzplan 2030

² Estimation of environmental costs in the areas of energy and transport, recommendations of the Federal Environment Agency, Germany, August 2013

2 Introduction

In the CULTURAL-E project, four representative multifamily residential buildings will be built in Norway, France, Germany and Italy as Residential Energy Plus Buildings. Different policies and related boundary conditions in each country have a great influence on the successful implementation of plus energy concepts. The current deliverable “National and local regulatory frame and boundary conditions” gives an overview of the legislation and requirements in each country and shows how they impact the spread of PEB concepts, with the help of a practical example.

Therefore, national funding schemes and local policies were analysed in regard to support renewable energy generation in buildings and favor the connection with the electric grid and other district buildings (e.g. direct delivery of power to neighbour buildings, grid feed-in) as well as the local energy market (e.g. energy prices, feed-in tariff) and foreseen developments and environmental aspects.

The present report summarized the results of this analysis. The results will be also included in the European Climate and Cultural Atlas for Plus Energy Building design (2CAP-Energy Atlas).

The content of the present deliverable is structured as follows:

2 National and local policies

The chapter provides an overview of national and local policies and building regulations in the CULTURAL-E four representative countries and their methods for the assessment of building energy concepts. It concludes with a comparison of the national building regulations and their target or limits values as well as the different boundaries for the building assessment.

3 National and local funding schemes

Different national and local funding schemes are available for promoting efficient building energy concepts, improved thermal insulations, integration of renewable energy systems (RES) or e-mobility in the building context.

4 Composition of price for electrical power

The report focuses on how the price for electrical power for households varies in Norway, France, Germany and Italy due to different price components, such as energy and distribution, network charges, taxes or VAT.

5 Options for electrical power marketing

In order to define business models for PEB, the knowledge of different options for marketing of electrical power on site is required. This chapter deals with options for self-consumption of locally generated electrical energy from onsite PV systems and available models for selling surplus energy, such as remunerations for feeding energy surplus from PV systems into the public grid.

6 Practical example

The case of a multifamily building, chosen as a fictive example, the impact on the energy costs at households level, caused by different energy prices, funding and remunerations for surplus photovoltaic energy fed into the public grid is assessed in Norway, France, Germany and Italy

7 Environmental Data

The composition of electricity production in Norway, France, Germany and Italy is shown together with their environmental impact, the global warming potential (GWP). They are described in kg CO₂ equivalent per kWh electrical power from public grid.

The conclusions of this report summarize the results of the analysis conducted about the “National and local regulatory frame and boundary conditions” for PEB design and performance, and they will be incorporated in the European Climate and Cultural Atlas for Plus Energy Building design (2CAP Energy Atlas).

3 National and local policies

3.1 Norway

Regulations on technical requirements for construction works (TEK 17)

In the "Regulations on technical requirements for construction works" (TEK 17) energy related requirements for new buildings are given in Chapter 14. This section presents the specific requirements on energy efficiency and renewable energy sources for residential buildings.

Energy efficiency requirements (§14-2)

For residential buildings there are two different options to meet the requirements for energy efficiency. The assessment of the energy requirements is done in accordance with the Norwegian Standard NS 3031:2014.

- 1) The building's total net energy requirement shall not exceed the following levels in kWh/(m²y) related to heated gross internal area
 - a) Single family house: 100 kWh + 1600/m² heated gross internal area
 - b) Multifamily house: 95 kWh/(m²y)

This includes net energy demand for space heating, ventilation heating, DHW, fans, pumps, lighting, technical equipment, space cooling and ventilation cooling. The total net energy is defined as the building's energy demand not including the efficiency of the energy supply system or distribution losses.

- 2) Residential buildings only: As an alternative to point 1) the energy efficiency requirements can be met by following the steps 1-9 below. The energy-saving measures may be departed from, provided that the building's thermal loss figures do not increase.

Table 1 Limit for heat transmission and infiltration loss of passive house

	Energy-saving measures	Single family house	Multifamily house
1.	U-value outer walls [W/(m ² K)]	≤ 0.18	≤ 0.18
2.	U-value roof [W/(m ² K)]	≤ 0.13	≤ 0.13
3.	U-value floors [W/(m ² K)]	≤ 0.10	≤ 0.10
4.	U-value windows and doors, including frames [W/(m ² K)]	≤ 0.80	≤ 0.80
5.	Proportion of window and door areas of heated gross internal area (%)	≤ 25	≤ 25
6.	Annual mean temperature efficiency ratio for heat	≥ 80	≥ 80

	Energy-saving measures	Single family house	Multifamily house
	recovery systems in ventilation systems (%)		
7.	Specific fan power (SFP) in ventilation systems [kW/(m ³ /s)]	≤ 1.5	≤ 1.5
8.	Air leakage rate per hour at 50 Pa pressure difference	≤ 0.6	≤ 0.6
9.	Normalised thermal bridge value, where m ² is stated as heated gross internal area [W/(m ² K)]	≤ 0.05	≤ 0.07

Minimum requirements (§14-3)

All new buildings need to fulfil the following minimum requirements:

- U-value outer walls: ≤ 0.22 W/m²K
- U-value roof: ≤ 0.18 W/m²K
- U-value floors on ground and open air: ≤ 0.18 W/m²K
- U-value windows and doors, including frames: ≤ 1.2 W/m²K
- Air leakage (at 50 Pa pressure differential): ≤ 1.5 (air change per hour)

Requirements for energy supply solutions (§14-4)

- 1) Installation of heating by fossil fuels is not permitted.
- 2) Buildings with a heated gross internal area > 1000 m² (except single family house) shall meet the following:
 - a) Have an energy-flexible heating system, and
 - b) Be adapted for use of low-temperature heating solutions.

This can be met by the following pre-accepted solution:

1. The energy-flexible system covers at least 60 % of the standardized net heating demand, calculated in accordance with NS 3031:2014.
2. Low-temperature energy-flexible heating systems must have a supply temperature of 60 °C or lower (not for DHW).
3. The size of the technical room for the heating plant should be calculated from the following equation: 10 m² + 1 % of BRA, up to 100 m².
4. Height from floor to ceiling should at least be 2.5 meter.

5. All doors into the technical room should have a clear width of at least 1.0 meters.
- 3) The requirements in the second paragraph do not apply to small houses. (4)
 - 4) Dwelling units in small houses (single family houses) must have a chimney. This requirement does not apply if:
 - a) the dwelling unit has a water-borne heating system; or
 - b) the annual net energy requirement for heating does not exceed the requirements for passive houses, calculated as specified in Norwegian Standard NS 3700:2013 Criteria for passive houses and low energy buildings – Residential buildings.

Exceptions and requirements for special projects (§14-5)

- 5) The general requirement relating to energy efficiency in section 14-2, first paragraph, may be increased by up to 10 kWh/(m²y). This requires that renewable electricity for the building is produced on the property, at least 20 kWh/(m²y).

Passive houses – residential buildings

Passive house standard is not a mandatory requirement for new buildings but can be seen as reference for PEB. Criteria for residential buildings is given in the Norwegian standard NS 3700:2013.

Table 2 shows the highest accepted heat loss number for heat transmission and infiltration loss.

Table 2 Limit for heat transmission and infiltration loss of passive house

	Limit for heat transmission and infiltration losses, W/(m ² K)		
	Residential building $A_{ri} < 100 \text{ m}^2$	Residential building $100 \text{ m}^2 \leq A_{ri} < 250 \text{ m}^2$	Residential building $A_{ri} \geq 250 \text{ m}^2$
Passive house	0.53	0.48	0.43

Criteria for heating covers room heating and ventilation heating. Heating demand is based on local climate and highest accepted net energy demand for heating depends on the yearly average temperature for the location. The calculation is done in accordance with the Norwegian Standard NS 3031:2014 and with standard values from NS 3700:2013.

The heating system should use other energy sources than fossil fuels and electricity. The calculated amount of delivered electricity and fossil fuels must be less than the total net energy demand when 50 % of net energy demand to DHW is subtracted.

Table 3 Highest accepted net energy demand for heating

Yearly mean temperature, θ_{ym}	Highest calculated net energy demand for heating, kWh/m ² /year	
	Residential building $A_{fl} < 250 \text{ m}^2$	Residential building $A_{fl} \geq 250 \text{ m}^2$
$\geq 6.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$15 + 5.4 * \frac{(250 - A_{fl})}{100}$	15
$< 6.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$15 + 5.4 * \frac{(250 - A_{fl})}{100} + (2.1 + 0.59 * \frac{(250 - A_{fl})}{100}) * (6.3 - \theta_{ym})$	$15 + 2.1 * (6.3 - \theta_{ym})$

Residential buildings should be designed to have acceptable thermal comfort without the need of room or ventilation cooling.

Minimum requirements for building components, technical components and air leakage:

- U-value windows and doors, including frames: $\leq 0.80 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K})$
- Normalised thermal bridge value: $\leq 0.03 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K})$
- Annual mean temperature efficiency ratio for heat recovery: $\geq 80 \%$
- Specific fan power (SFP) for ventilation system: $\leq 1.5 \text{ kW}/(\text{m}^3/\text{s})$
- Air leakage rate per hour at 50 Pa: $\leq 0.60 \text{ 1/h}$

3.2 France

The French “Thermal regulations”

Current RT2012

The last “thermal regulation” (2012) in force today allows to move from a requirement of means (not to exceed a value of maximum coefficient of transmission defined by wall) to a requirement of results on the primary energy consumption. Indeed, the maximum consumption for the five uses (heating, domestic hot water, cooling, ventilation, lighting) is no longer determined compared to a reference according to the building, but fixed at a limit for primary energy³ of 50 kWh/(m²y) (5 uses, see Figure 1) adjustable according to the geographical area. A Bbio⁴ coefficient allows more attention to be paid to the design of the building and encourages bioclimatic design by promoting compactness,

³ France: factors to convert final energy to primary energy: wood: 1; gaz: 1; elec: 2,58; sun: 0

⁴ Bâtiment bioclimatique (FR) = Bioclimatic Building (EN)

solar gain, visual comfort with natural lighting, thermal inertia and orientation. An indicator for the conventional indoor temperature “Tic” (Température Intérieure Conventiennelle) is used to determine summer comfort and to avoid overheat. The Tic calculation is kept and the number of safeguards (minimum requirements for thermal resistance or thermal bridges) is reduced. The expected gain in terms of overall energy consumption is 50 % compared to RT2005.

Figure 1 Evolution of French thermal regulation

Energy efficiency requirements are presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Table of minimum requirements

Insulation	<p>Roof Thermal resistance > 8 m².K/W Ground Thermal resistance > 4 m².K/W Wall Thermal resistance > 4 m².K/W</p>
Air leakage	<p>The measured air permeability of the envelope of the frame makes it possible to evaluate the leakage rate under 4 Pascal. Noted Q4 Pa surf (official value of air permeability), this value must be less than or equal to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • individual house: 0.6 m³/h.m² of cold walls excluding low floors • apartment building: 1 m³/h.m² of cold walls excluding low floor if the measurement is made on the whole building and 0.8 m³/h.m² of loss walls excluding low floor if the measurement is made by sampling the building <p>A blower door test must be carried out to obtain the RT2012 certificate. If the infiltration rate is higher than the value specified above, corrective work must be carried out and a second test will verify that the infiltration rate is now regulatory. It is therefore advisable to carry out at least one intermediate blower door following the installation of the windows, in the presence of the various trades, in order to agree together on any corrective work before finishing work.</p>
Thermal bridges	<p>The overall average linear thermal transmission of the thermal bridges of the building must not exceed 0.28 W/(ml.K) and the average linear thermal transmission coefficient of the intermediate floor/walls connections must not exceed 0.6 W/(ml.K).</p>
Systems	<p>Any individual house must use a renewable energy source for the production of domestic hot water (or DHW). The client can choose one of the following solutions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solar thermal DHW • Connection to a heating network operating > 50% renewable energy • Thermodynamic DHW • Heat pump • Micro-cogeneration

Next RT2020

The next thermal regulation expected for 2020 should take a further step by generalizing the construction of positive energy buildings (BEPOS) which produce more energy than they consume (Figure 1). The arrival of these regulations is prepared in advance by the construction industry because it implies in particular a performance guarantee.

What positive energy buildings should have:

- Heating consumption must be less than 12 kWh/(m²y) of primary energy
- Total energy consumption less than 100 kWh/(m²y) of primary energy for all = 5 uses + appliances
- The ability to produce energy to have a positive energy balance on the five 5 uses (excepted appliances) using photovoltaic panels for example.

3.3 Germany

National policies that support or adverse renewable energy generation in buildings are shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2 Overview of local policies Germany

Energy Saving Ordinance (EnEV 2014)

New buildings have to fulfil the requirements of the current version of the “Energy Saving Ordinance (EnEV 1014). For the building evaluation the energy consumption for building heating, domestic hot water production, auxiliaries (e.g. heating pumps) and ventilation is taken into account. Energy consumption for cooling is only taken into account for non residential buildings. User electricity for lighting and household appliances is not part of the balance. The building evaluation is based on the calculation method according to DIN V 18599. It is a so-called "reference building method" without a fixed value for the primary energy consumption of the building. There is a limit value for buildings of primary energy consumption and limit value for the thermal insulation of the building envelope.

EEWärmeG and EWärmeG

The law for the promotion of renewable energies (EE) in the heating sector “Renewable Energies Heat Act (EEWärmeG 2014)” applies nationwide and is mandatory to all new buildings as well as to renovated public buildings.

The fulfillment options for all new buildings are:

- 15 % Solar thermal energy
- 30 % Biogas in CHP (combined heat and power)
- 50 % Biogas, biomass, geothermal energy or ambient heat
- Alternative measures:
 - improved building insulation (HT´ EnEV -15 %)
 - 50% combined heat and power or use of waste heat
 - district heating with share of 50 % renewable energy

The local “Renewable Heat Act” (EWärmeG 2015) in Baden-Württemberg states that a certain share of building energy needs must be covered by renewable energies.

The fulfillment options for residential buildings are:

- Solar thermal energy: $0.06- 0.07 \text{ m}^2_{\text{Coll.}}/\text{m}^2_{\text{living space}}$ (multifamily building, single family building)
- central heating with biomass or heat pump (SPF > 3.5)
- improved building insulation (EnEV -20 %)
- CHP: min. $15 \text{ kWh}_{\text{el}}/\text{m}^2_{\text{living space}}$
- District heating with 50% CHP or 15 % renewable energies/ waste heat
- Photovoltaic: $0.02 \text{ kWp}/\text{m}^2_{\text{living space}}$
- Combination of measures, partly fulfilment with renovation roadmap

Building Energy Act (GEG 2020)

The EU Building Directive (2010) requires the target nearly zero energy buildings (nZEB) from 2019 for new public buildings and from 2021 for all new buildings. Therefore the new building energy act (GEG 2020) is planned to come into force soon. It merges the rules EnEG, EEWärmeG and EnEV which are still running in parallel. The requirements for new buildings are not tightened.

Other Building Standards

In addition to the legal requirements, there are other established building energy standards such as “KfW efficiency houses” (KfW bank), “Passive house” or “Efficiency house Plus” (BBSR). The requirements based on the respective boundaries are listed in Table 5.

Table 5 Requirements of building energy standards

Building energy standard	Requirements	Boundaries
KfW efficiency house 55	55 % primary energy demand, 70 % HT' compared to reference building (EnEV)	Building energy demand (EnEV)
KfW efficiency house 40	40 % primary energy demand, 55 % HT' compared to reference building (EnEV)	
KfW efficiency house 40 Plus	see KfW 40 and PV + battery, ventilation with heat recovery and user interface,	
Passive house	Primary energy demand: max. 60 kWh/(m ² y) Heating demand: max. 15 kWh/(m ² y)	Building energy demand (EnEV) + user energy demand
Efficiency house Plus, BBSR	Final and primary energy demand > 0	Building energy demand (EnEV) + user energy demand

Law for the expansion of renewable energies (EEG 2017)

The aim of this law is to increase the share of electricity generated from renewable energies in gross electricity consumption in steps to at least 80 % by 2050. Among other things, the EEG stipulates the remuneration for electricity fed into the grid from photovoltaic systems see Table 22 in chapter 6.3.

Tenant Electricity Act

The Tenant Electricity Act (Mieterstromgesetz) is funding the direct use of produced power from photovoltaics (max. 100 kWp) on site for tenants. The renter's electricity surcharge is linked to the amount of the feed-in tariff via a discount amount of 8.5 ct/kWh respectively 8 ct/kWh for plants > 40 kWp. Since the feed-in tariff for photovoltaic plants according to EEG drops monthly, the subsidy will soon be ineffective see also Table 22.

3.4 Italy

The main legislative references at national level are **The Ministerial Decree 26 June 2015 "Minimum building requirements"**, reporting the requirements of the envelope and HVAC (Heating, Ventilation, Air Conditioning) system and the **Legislative Decree 28/2011 "Promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources"** dealing with the installation of photovoltaic and solar thermal systems. In addition, several Italian regions established a set of requirements at local level, according to the specificities of the context.

In particular, in the Emilia-Romagna region, where the Mediterranean demo case is located, the legislative reference is the **D.G.R. 967/2015, updated with D.G.R. 1715/2016, “Definition of minimum energy performance requirements”**.

The requirements for nearly zero energy buildings (for new constructions) are given at national level:

- a) Compliance with all the following requirements of the Decree 26 June 2015 "Minimum building requirements", Appendix A:
 - 1. limit values of H'T less than values in Table 7;
 - 2. summer equivalent solar area limit values ($A_{sol, est} / A_{sup\ utile}$) less than values in Table 11 Appendix A; overall and partial energy performance higher than those of the reference building⁵; average efficiencies of the generation subsystems lower than those of the reference building (Table 8 and Table 9)
- b) Compliance with the integration obligations of renewable sources pursuant to Legislative Decree 3 March 2011, n. 28 (Annex 3, paragraph 1, letter c).

The same requests apply to new buildings and deep renovations in case of interventions on the building envelope that interest > 50 % of the total gross area of the building dispersant and contemporary renovation or new installation of the winter and/or summer air conditioning heating system for the entire building.

Ministry Decree 26/06/2015: Promotion of the improvement of the energy performance of buildings

The energetic performance is substantially defined through performance indexes related to the envelope and to every energy provision.

The indexes of useful thermal performance for heating, useful thermal performance for cooling and overall energy performance of the building must be lower than the values of the corresponding limit indexes calculated for reference building.

Table 6 Energetic performance indexes and parameters

$H'T$ in W/m^2K	Average global heat exchange coefficient for transmission per unit of dispersing surface ($H'T$)
$A_{sol\ equ} / A_{usable\ area}$	Summer equivalent solar area for usable surface unit
$EP_{H, nd}$ in $kWh/(m^2y)$	Thermal performance index functional for heating
η_H	Thermal performance index useful for heating

⁵ By **reference building** we mean an identical building in terms of geometry (shape, volumes, floor area, surfaces of construction elements and components), orientation, territorial location, intended use and boundary situation and having thermal characteristics and energy parameters predetermined, for which the requirements of the building being designed are checked.

$EP_{H,nd}$ in kWh/(m ² y)	Average seasonal efficiency of the winter air conditioning system
$EP_{W,nd}$ in kWh/(m ² y)	Thermal performance index functional for domestic hot water
η_w	Average seasonal efficiency of the domestic hot water system
EP_w in kWh/(m ² y)	Energy performance index for domestic hot water production
EP_v in kWh/(m ² y)	Energy performance index for ventilation
$EP_{C,nd}$ in kWh/(m ² y)	Thermal performance index functional for cooling
η_c	Average seasonal efficiency of the summer air conditioning system
EP_c in kWh/(m ² y)	Energy performance index for summer air conditioning
EP_L in kWh/(m ² y)	Energy performance index for artificial lighting. This index is not calculated for category E1, with the exception of colleges, convents, penal houses, barracks and for category E1 (3)
EP_T in kWh/(m ² y)	Energy performance index of the service for the transport of people and things (elevators, sidewalks and escalators). This index is not calculated for category E1, with the exception of colleges, convents, penal houses, barracks and for category E1 (3)
$EP_{gl,tot} + EP_{w,tot} + EP_{v,tot} + EP_{L,tot} + EP_{T,tot}$ in kWh/(m ² y)	Overall energy performance index of the building, expressed in total non-renewable primary energy.

The **average global heat exchange coefficient for transmission per unit of dispersing surface (HT')** must be lower than the limit values indicated in the following table⁶; in the Emilia-Romagna region there are climatic zones D, E and F (the demo is located in climatic zone E, the most widespread in the region and in the national territory).

Table 7 Max. value of the average global HT' in W/m²K

SHAPE REPORT (S/V)	Climatic Zone				
	A e B	C	D	E	F
$S/V \geq 0,7$	0,58	0,55	0,53	0,50	0,48
$0,7 > S/V \geq 0,74$	0,63	0,60	0,58	0,55	0,53
$0,4 > S/V$	0,80	0,80	0,80	0,75	0,70
TYPE OF INTERVENTION	A e B	C	D	E	F
Enlargement and important second level renovation for all building types	0,73	0,70	0,68	0,65	0,62

The **summer equivalent solar area** limit values ($A_{sol,est} / A_{sup\ utile}$) must be lower than the limit values indicated in the following table.⁷

Table 8 Max. value of the average global HT' in W/m²K

Building type	All climatic zones
Type E.1 except for colleges, convents, houses of punishment, barracks as well as the category E.1(3)	≤0,030
All other buildings	≤0,040

⁶ Table 10 of Appendix A of the Ministry Decree 26/06/2015

⁷ Table 11 of Appendix A of the Ministry Decree 26/06/2015

The **overall and partial energy performance requirements** are verified using the reference building method.

The energy performance indexes $EP_{H,nd}$, $EP_{C,nd}$ and $EP_{gl,tot}$ must be lower than the values of the corresponding limit indices of the reference building ($EP_{H,nd,limit}$, $EP_{C,nd,limit}$ and $EP_{gl,tot,limit}$).

Plant efficiency values, η_u (useful efficiency) and η_{gn} (generation efficiency), of the heating, sanitary water and cooling services must be lower than the limit values of the reference building indicated in the following tables:

Table 9 Average efficiencies η_u of subsystems of use of reference building⁸

Efficienza dei sottosistemi di utilizzazione η_u:	H	C	W
Distribuzione idronica	0,81	0,81	0,70
Distribuzione aeraulica	0,83	0,83	-
Distribuzione mista	0,82	0,82	-

⁸ Table 7 of Appendix A of the Ministry Decree 26/06/2015

Table 10 Average efficiencies η_{gn} of generation subsystems of reference building⁹

	Produzione di energia termica			Produzione di energia elettrica in situ
	H	C	W	
Sottosistemi di generazione:				
- Generatore a combustibile liquido	0,82	-	0,80	-
- Generatore a combustibile gassoso	0,95	-	0,85	-
- Generatore a combustibile solido	0,72	-	0,70	-
- Generatore a biomassa solida	0,72	-	0,65	-
- Generatore a biomassa liquida	0,82	-	0,75	-
- Pompa di calore a compressione di vapore con motore elettrico	3,00	(*)	2,50	-
- Macchina frigorifera a compressione di vapore a motore elettrico	-	2,50	-	-
- Pompa di calore ad assorbimento	1,20	(*)	1,10	-
- Macchina frigorifera a fiamma indiretta	-	$0,60 \times \eta_{gn}$ (**)	-	-
- Macchina frigorifera a fiamma diretta	-	0,60	-	-
- Pompa di calore a compressione di vapore a motore endotermico	1,15	1,00	1,05	-
- Cogeneratore	0,55	-	0,55	0,25
- Riscaldamento con resistenza elettrica	1,00	-	-	-
- Teleriscaldamento	0,97	-	-	-
- Teleraffrescamento	-	0,97	-	-
- Solare termico	0,3	-	0,3	-
- Solare fotovoltaico	-	-	-	0,1
- Mini colico e mini idroelettrico	-	-	-	(**)
NOTA: Per i combustibili tutti i dati fanno riferimento al potere calorifico inferiore				
(*) Per pompe di calore che prevedono la funzione di raffrescamento di considera lo stesso valore delle macchine frigorifere della stessa tipologia				
(**) si assume l'efficienza media del sistema installato nell'edificio reale				

Legislative Decree 28/2011: Promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources

The decree introduces the following obligations to integrate renewable sources:

- a) Contributions of thermal energy:
- 50 % of the sanitary water demand;
 - 50 % of the sum of the total sanitary water, heating and cooling demand

⁹ Table 8 of Appendix A of the Ministry Decree 26/06/2015

- b) Electricity production, contemporary respect of:
- installed electrical power $P > 1$ kW per residential unit and $P > 0.5$ kW per 100 m² of useful energy area of buildings for non-residential use
 - installed electrical power $P > S_q / 50$ (S_q in m² = covered area of the building).

The local policy “**D.G.R. 967/2015**”, updated with **D.G.R. 1715/2016**, faithfully reproduces the provisions of the “DM 26/06/2015” and the “Legislative Decree 28/2011”.

3.5 Summary and Conclusion

Table 11 shows an overview of the building regulations of each country and the respective boundaries for the building assessment of residential buildings.

Table 11 Overview regulations and boundaries for building assessment

	Regulation	specification	Balance limit for building
NOR	Regulations on technical requirements for construction works (TEK 17)	Useful energy demand ≤ 95 kWh/(m ² *a)* Limit U-values for building components *Multi family house	
FR	Thermal regulation (2015)	Primary energy ≤ 50 kWh/(m ² *a) Limit value HT ⁻	
	Next thermal regulation (exp.2020)	Primary energy heating ≤ 12 kWh/(m ² *a) Final energy ≤ 100 kWh/(m ² *a) + RES for Plus energy balance (PE)	
GER	ENEV 2016 (GEG exp.2020)	Limit value HT ⁻ and Primary energy Building reference method	
	EEWärmeG (GEG exp.2020)	15-50 % RES for heating/cooling depending on source, alternatives e.g. HT ⁻ -15 %	
IT	Ministry Decree 26/06/2009	Limit value HT ⁻ and Primary energy Building reference method	
	DLgs 28/2011	50% RES of total expected consumption > 1 kWp PV per residential unit	

Norway and France have fixed values for the limit of useful, final or primary energy demand. Germany and Italy use the building reference method without a fixed value. For residential buildings, Germany assesses only the buildings energy demand for building heating, domestic hot water, ventilation and auxiliaries. Italy and Norway also include energy for building cooling. Whereas, France assesses the energy demand of cooling and lighting of the building. The electricity demand of household appliances, the so-called users’ energy demand, is not part of any building assessment.

The regulations for building assessments use different boundaries, fixed or variable values for the overall limit of buildings energy demand and assess different effect units from useful, final to primary energy. Not any country assesses the effective greenhouse gas emissions of building energy concepts.

For the PEB standards according to CULTURAL-E a uniform boundary is defined, including the assessment of all buildings energy demand considering building heating, domestic hot water, ventilation, auxiliaries, building cooling, lighting and user appliances with a fixed value for the greenhouse gas emissions of $\leq 2 \text{ kgCO}_2/(\text{m}^2\text{y})$.

The EU Building Directive (2010) requires the nZEB standard for new buildings from 2019 for public buildings and 2021 for all new buildings. On behalf of the European Commission, ECOFYS analysed 2014 the status quo of national building regulations of EU countries and their effort on the application of a nearly zero energy buildings standard. The final report is available online¹⁰. As an example, in Germany the requirements for nZEB are considered to be fulfilled with the current EnEV 2016. A typical German multifamily house realized in EnEV 2016 standard still leads to CO₂ emissions of about 40 kgCO₂/(m²y), which is far from the expected emission rate of plus energy houses. The planned GEG does not provide for any stricter requirements in 2020, but the mandatory reporting of CO₂ emissions from buildings in energy certificates is a first step in making progress towards achieving climate protection goals in the building sector visible. But, in order to achieve a real steering effect, a fixed CO₂ target value for buildings would have to be set instead of maintaining the previous assessment of reference buildings and the primary energy requirement (see Mahler 2018). France and Norway already use fix targets for the energy consumptions of buildings. In case of Norway, the steering effect towards climate neutral buildings is given by a target limit for the useful energy demand in combination with banning fossils fuels for heating devices and a renewable based power production also for electricity from grid. In the next thermal regulation, France aims at plus energy building based on positive primary energy balance for building operation except user appliances by using renewable energy production on site. This is also a positive step towards PEB. But, a CO₂ target value for residential buildings which could lead to measurable CO₂ reductions in the building sector is not planned yet. All building regulations (Table 11) do not include the entire energy consumption of a building on site. The boundaries for building evaluation has to be expanded by the proportion of embodied energy for building construction and the energy requirement for building operation, including user appliances. A future CO₂ target value for residential buildings must include these boundaries. In order to further expand the use of self-generated electricity from locally generated PV power and to promote sector coupling by building up the infrastructure, it is also sensible in the medium term to assess e-mobility.

For the desired coupling of the electricity, heating and mobility sectors, the introduction of district level approaches compared to an individual assessment of buildings is a crucial aspect. By implementing energy systems for districts with the generation and storage of renewable energies as well as the provision of local heat and electricity for

¹⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/Updated%20progress%20report%20NZEB.pdf>

buildings and mobility, CO₂ savings can be achieved going beyond the individual building approach. A district level approach also makes other important aspects possible, such as energy storage and flexibility in demand and generation, and thus contributing to grid stabilization.

4 National and local funding schemes

4.1 Norway

Enova is the national company who can allocate funding for energy efficiency and energy production (owned by the Ministry of Climate and Environment). Only private householders can receive direct funding for RES.

From 1. July 2020 the funding is the following¹¹:

- Electricity production/ PV systems: 750 € + 125 €/kW (max 15 kW).
- Solar collectors: 500 € + 200 €/m² (max 25 m²)
- Also some types of heat pumps and bio boiler can receive funding.

Elsertifikater (Electricity certificate market):

- Common plan with Sweden for installation of large-scale renewable production plants; mainly relevant for large scale PV systems, hydropower, wind etc.;
- Registered production plants get a market price for the electricity produced;
- Market price for certificates varies between 0.004 – 0.02 €/kWh.

4.2 France

The Effinergie Association is the reference for all funding and subsidies (national, local initiatives regions by regions) to guide owners and decision makers.

¹¹ Change rate 1 € = 10 NOK

Figure 3 View of Effinergie Data base¹²

PEB have to become the construction standard from 2020 with the entry into force of RE2020 (RT=Thermal Regulation that will become the RE = Environmental Regulation taking into account the carbon impact).

The additional cost compared to a conventional building is estimated at 20 %. Nevertheless, a PEB is associated to a set of advantages:

- it is possible to sell the surplus energy;
- the energy bill is greatly reduced compared to a conventional building;
- the real estate value increases.

Most of the aid in France are related to the renovation of existing buildings, which represents the major challenge (Figure 3). Nevertheless, there are also policies for boosting the uptake of PEB target (for both new projects and refurbishments):

PTZ – Zero Rate Loan

The eco PTZ device is a zero-rate loan that helps individuals renovate/built their homes to improve energy performance. Accessible without means test until December 31st, 2018, this loan can reach 30'000 €.

¹² <https://www.effinergie.org/web/les-aides-financieres>

They can finance:

- Efficient thermal insulation work on the roof (including from the outside,
- Efficient thermal insulation works on walls facing the outside,
- Efficient thermal insulation work on glass walls and doors to the outside,
- Installation, regulation or replacement work of heating systems, cases associated with economic and efficient ventilation systems or efficient domestic hot water production,
- Installation work of heating equipment using a renewable energy source,
- Installation work of domestic hot water production equipment using a renewable energy source.

You can benefit from this loan if:

- You build and buy land or if you acquire new housing never occupied before,
- You acquire an already existing accommodation whatever its age, and if you finance renovation works,
- You transform a room you already own into housing.

The accommodation for which you are requesting a 0-rate loan must be your main residence within one year of the completion of the work or the acquisition of your accommodation.

Exemption from property tax

If the new housing was completed after January 1st, 2009 and its overall energy performance level is higher than RT2012, it is possible to benefit, under certain conditions, from a temporary exemption from Land tax of at least 5 years.

Regional aid

There are local initiatives, regional, departmental, or even municipal aid schemes. It is necessary to inquire locally even if most of them are referenced on the Effinergie data base (Figure 3).

Important

Any financial assistance or tax benefit related to the energy transition implies to go through a company or craftsman certified RGE (Recognized Guarantor of the Environment).

4.3 Germany

Figure 4 Overview of funding schemes in Germany

KfW Efficiency houses

The KfW Bank is funding energy efficient buildings according to the KfW building energy standards in the form of low-interest loans or investment grants (see Table 12). Energy efficient buildings are defined by a combination of measures on building insulation and plants to reduce HT` and Primary Energy of building in comparison to minimum requirements according to national law (EnEV) see requirements in chapter 3.3.

Table 12 KfW fundings for new residential buildings (153)¹³

Building energy standard	Funding (here investment grant)
KfW efficiency house 55	max. 18.000 € per unit
KfW efficiency house 40	max. 24.000 € per unit
KfW efficiency house 40 Plus	max. 30.000 € per unit

13

[https://www.kfw.de/inlandsfoerderung/Privatpersonen/Neubau/Finanzierungsangebote/Energieeffizient-Bauen-\(153\)/](https://www.kfw.de/inlandsfoerderung/Privatpersonen/Neubau/Finanzierungsangebote/Energieeffizient-Bauen-(153)/)

Other national fundings for new buildings

- Small compact fuel cell devices with 0.25 – 5 kW_{el}: investment grant for installation and device depending on electrical power (max. € 28'200) for new and existing buildings, KfW programme 433¹⁴,
- Photovoltaic plants, battery systems: low-interest loans, KfW programme 270¹⁵,
- Solar thermal plant, biomass and heat pump with special requirements, BAFA¹⁶.

Other local fundings (Baden-Wuerttemberg)

- E-Mobility: € 3'000 – 5'000 funding per unit, L-Bank¹⁷

4.4 Italy

Photovoltaic plant

Tax deductions for photovoltaic plant costs (included storage) as an annual measure which is normally repeated.

- a) for existing buildings:
 - Deduction on taxes paid annually on income (repayments divided into 10 years),
 - Deduction of 50 % of the sustained costs, VAT 10 % (rather than 22 %).

b) for new buildings: no tax deductions but VAT reduction: 4 % VAT

E-Mobility

Tax deduction of 50 % in 10 years for the expenses incurred to purchase and install a charging station for electric vehicles.¹⁸

The expenses documented must deal with:

- Purchase of the charging station,

¹⁴

[https://www.kfw.de/inlandsfoerderung/Privatpersonen/Neubau/F%C3%B6rderprodukte/Energieeffizient-Bauen-und-Sanieren-Zuschuss-Brennstoffzelle-\(433\)/](https://www.kfw.de/inlandsfoerderung/Privatpersonen/Neubau/F%C3%B6rderprodukte/Energieeffizient-Bauen-und-Sanieren-Zuschuss-Brennstoffzelle-(433)/)

¹⁵ [https://www.kfw.de/inlandsfoerderung/Privatpersonen/Neubau/F%C3%B6rderprodukte/Erneuerbare-Energien-\(270\)/](https://www.kfw.de/inlandsfoerderung/Privatpersonen/Neubau/F%C3%B6rderprodukte/Erneuerbare-Energien-(270)/)

¹⁶

https://www.bafa.de/DE/Energie/Heizen_mit_Erneuerbaren_Energien/Foerdervoraussetzungen/foerdervoraussetzungen_node.html

¹⁷ <https://www.l-bank.de/produkte/finanzhilfen/bw-e-gutschein.html>

¹⁸ budget law 2019, expenses documented and incurred from 1 March 2019 to 31 December 2021

- Installation of the charging station,
- increase in meter power (up to a maximum of 7 kW).

The maximum deduction is € 1'500 (maximum amount of expenses on which to calculate the 50 % tax deduction of € 3'000).

In Italy, there are no specific funding schemes for new energy efficient buildings, nZEB or PEB. Further funding schemes such as “Conto termico” for production of thermal energy from RES and new tax incentives for PV, EE storage and car charging infrastructure are only for the deep renovation of existing buildings.

4.5 Summary and Conclusion

In all countries analysed there are numerous funding programs for measures such as building standards, heating systems based on renewable energies, insulation of the building envelope, photovoltaic systems, or e-mobility.

So far, there exists no funding for alternative construction methods, although a lightweight or hybrid construction causes far lower CO₂ emissions than a solid construction in reinforced concrete or masonry.

In addition, the large number of existing subsidies is not always made use of and the effective CO₂ savings of the measures are nor transparent or proved to be enough. **Future funding programs should subsidise CO₂-saving energy concepts instead of individual measures.** This could be an obligation to (i) pay taxes when targets according to the individual climate protection plans are not met; or (ii) a subsidization of real CO₂ savings, if they are already being achieved beyond the targets.

CO₂ pricing of energy sources across all sectors is an effective measure as well. According to the polluter pays principle, the external costs would be borne where they are caused. Building owners and users would act in a climate-friendly manner in their own interest because the costs for the use of fossil fuels would rise sharply. CO₂ pricing for fossil fuels for heat and transport of 25 per ton CO₂ will be introduced in Germany by 2021.¹⁹ Due to protests of sections of the public, the announced CO₂ tax in France is currently pending. In order to develop a real steering effect in reducing the greenhouse potential, the costs for climate change negative impacts must be correspondingly high. The German Federal Environment Agency recommended 180 € per tonCO₂ with an increase up to 240 € per tonCO₂ by 2050 (UBA 2013)²⁰.

¹⁹ Klimaschutzplan 2030

²⁰ Estimation of environmental costs in the areas of energy and transport, recommendations of the Federal Environment Agency, Germany, August 2013

5 Composition of price for electrical power

5.1 Norway

The average price for electricity in Norway for private households in 2019 is 0.12 €/kWh²¹. The pricing model for electricity in Norway is going through a review and the pricing model will be changed. The final version is not yet known but it is likely that it will move towards a power-based tariff, rather than just paying for used energy.

Table 13 Electricity price, Norway 2019

Tariff	€/kWh	Source
Electricity spot price	0.05	SSB – average price for households in Norway, 2019 ²²
Grid tariff	0.03	
Government taxes + VAT	0.04	

5.2 France

In France two options for households exist: It is possible to choose between a constant or a dynamic pricing option (Figure 6). The idea is to encourage consumers to reduce their consumption during the hours when demand is usually very high, and to postpone this consumption during hours of low use by offering a lower kWh price for these off-peak hours (15 % less). The pricing option is linked with nuclear power production which continues to produce whatever the demand. The consumer benefits from a privileged off-peak rate for 8 hours a day and ERDF (French network manager) can more easily regulate its traffic and manage with peak consumption. Dynamic pricing option represents 60 % of the volume (Figure 5).

²¹ exchange rate Feb. 2020: 1 € = 9,7 NOK

²²<https://www.ssb.no/energi-og-industri/artikler-og-publikasjoner/nok-et-ar-med-hoye-strompriser-for-husholdninger>

Figure 5 Distribution of electricity sales. Source: EDF activity report 2017

Figure 6 Average electricity prices in France

Note about dynamic pricing: around 45 % of EDF (Electricité De France) electricity meters for individuals are equipped with the Peak/Off-Peak (HPHC) tariff option. This option allows to benefit from the cheaper electricity prices at certain times (off-peak hours) against the more expensive prices at peak hours. But it is impossible to determine the off-peak hours: it is, in fact, the distribution network manager who is in charge of

fixing these time slots locally according to the production conditions at the different times of the day. The subscription cost is also higher (column 2 vs column 1 in Figure 6).

Figure 7 Electricity price components

Production costs refer to costs related to the production of electricity (in a nuclear power plant by other sources). 75 % of electricity production in France is nuclear and comes from EDF power plants.

TURPE: The grid costs are financed by TURPE, the Tariff for the Use of Public Electricity Networks, paid by the customer either indirectly via the electricity bill (for small consumers) or directly to the electricity network operator in the case of direct contact with the network operator (large consumers in general)

CSPE (Contribution to the Public Electricity Service): finances the development of renewable energies, tariff equalization and the basic necessity tariff. In 2018, its cost was 22.5 €/MWh.

TVA: 20 % on the price per kWh and 5.5 % on the subscription.

TCFE: the tax on the final consumption of electricity is a local tax paid to the municipalities and departments. It is capped at 9.56€/MWh in 2018.

CTA (transmission tariff contribution): 27.04 % of the fixed part of the TURPE. It finances the specific rights relating to old-age insurance for employees in the electricity and gas industries.

5.3 Germany

The average price for electricity according to BMWi in 2019 amounted to 31.24 ct/kWh including VAT. The following example shows the components of the electricity price from

the local energy supplier of the German demo case in Eislingen/Fils which is slightly below the German average.

Figure 8 Composition of price for electrical power from grid for household

Energy price = electricity generation costs through purchasing and self-production

Accounting and distribution = cost for electricity supplier

EEG levy = tax to finance the expansion of renewable energies (6.76 ct/kWh, Dec. 2019). It has to be paid also for direct use of produced power from photovoltaics on site: depending on size and ownership (0 - 100 %), see chapter 6.3.

Electricity tax = a federally regulated excise tax on electricity.

Network charges = a fee that every network user who conducts electricity through the supply network must pay to the network operator.

§ 18 AbLaV = Covering the costs of providing and switching off loads

CHP levy = serves to cover costs from the promotion of combined heat and power plants

Concession levy = Fee for network operators for the use of public roads and routes for laying power lines paid to municipalities.

§ 19 levy = Compensation for lost revenue from the electricity distribution networks

Offshore grid allocation = Covering costs from the construction and operation of offshore connection lines as well as compensation for disruptions or delays in connection lines

VAT = Value added tax on all electricity prices is 19 %

5.4 Italy

In Italy, a household can typically choose between a contract with fixed or variable price for electrical energy, see Table 14.

Table 14 Type of contract for electricity for households

Type of contract	Timeslot	
Fixed prices	Unique timeslot	
Timeslot price (Two-time priced)	Slot F1	From 8 to 19 on Monday to Friday, excluding national holidays
	Slot F23	From 19 to 8 in the days from Monday to Friday and all hours of the days on Saturdays, Sundays and national holidays

There are currently different types of market: “free market” (prevalent and continuously growing share), “market with greater protection” and “safeguard market” (for weak users; from 2022 it will absorb the “greater protection market”).

In the “greater protection market” (only for domestic user and other low-use voltage), contractual and economic conditions are established by the Authority of energy.

In the “free market”, some contractual conditions established by the Authority (ex: default, recess), while other contractual conditions and all economic conditions are established by the seller. Besides, there is a specific type offer of the free market named “PLACET” (with fixed prices or timeslot prices) in which all contractual conditions are established by the Authority and all economic conditions established by the seller.

In the “free market”, situations can be extremely differentiated (by seller, buyer, offer, etc.), difficult to schematize. The conditions of the “greater protection market” are described below.

Table 15 Electrical energy prices

Prices for 1 January - 31 March 2020	Energy matter			Transmission, distribution and measurement	System charges
	Fixed prices	Two-time priced			
	Unique slot	Slot F1	Slot F23		
Energy share (ct/kWh)	7.092	7.666	6.799	0.833	4.1817
Fixed share (€/y)	51.1409			20.4	-
Power share (€/kW/y)	-			20.88	-
Discount for e-bill & electronic payment	6 euro/year				

The composition of price for electrical power (protected market) for a typical domestic consumer (family with 3 kW of committed power and 2'700 kWh of annual consumption) is shown in Table 16 and Table 17 below.

Table 16 Cost components of electricity purchased (Households, 1.Q 2020)

Price components			Tot weight	Description
Expense for the energy matter	Fixed quote	[€/y]	45.7%	36.1% Supply 9.6 % Retail
	Energy quote	[€/kWh]		
Transmission, distribution and measurement (management of the meter) tariffs	Fixed quote	[€/y]	19.8%	
	Power quote	[€/kW/a]		
	Energy quote	[€/kWh]		
Expense for system charges	Energy quote	[€/kWh]	21.3%	
	Fixed quote	[€/y]		

Price components			Tot weight	Description
Excise duties		[0,0227 €/kWh]	4.2	13.2 % taxes
VAT (10%)			9%	
Total			100	

Table 17 Expenditure by type of consumer (Households, 1.Q. 2020, fixed price during day)

Yearly consumption (kWh)	Costs Profile type (fixed price)	kWh Costs without tax [ct/kWh]	kWh Costs tax included [ct/kWh]
Committed power 3 kW			
1500	312.30	20.82	23.98
2200	395.42	17.97	20.70
2700	454.80	16.84	19.40
3200	514.17	16.07	18.51
Committed power 4,5 kW			
3500	581.12	16.60	19.12
Committed power 6 kW			
6000	909.30	15.16	17.46

Profile type: Fixed prices and prices by timeslot are the same if the percentage breakdown of consumption is as shown in the following table.

Table 18 Profile Type with share of annual consumption

% in Timeslot F1	% in Timeslot F2	% in Timeslot F3
33 %	31 %	36 %

5.5 Summary and Conclusion

An overview of the prices for electrical energy for households in Germany, France, Norway and Italy is shown in Figure 9 below. Whereas the prices in Norway and France are comparatively low, the households in Italy and Germany have to pay double the price. The reasons are the high taxes in Germany, including the EEG-levy and high charges for network and energy & distribution in Italy.

Figure 9 Composition of price for electrical power for households
(FOR ITALY, "FREE MARKET" CASE)

Further variable pricing options depending on time are offered in France and Italy (where there are also different types of market, see § 5.4). In France, the variable pricing option is linked with the nuclear power production. By offering a low off-peak rate for 8 hours a day, the power consumption can be postponed and thus can help the French energy system to better manage the peak of consumption. In Italy, the intention to offer variable rates is to benefit those who consume energy not at peak times.

Variable electricity tariffs for consumers can support a renewable energy supply.

Such a pricing system aims to reduce peak loads, to make a better use of renewable energies and to reduce the energy costs of the consumer. Many electricity providers already offer a variable electricity tariff, which is divided into 2 - 3 tariff levels (day, night, and weekend tariff). However, the energy supply provided by wind and solar systems fluctuates strongly within one day. Also, the experts are, therefore, calling for tariffs that calculate the electricity costs from the current electricity prices (Agora Energiewende

2017)²³. Studies show that the switch to variable electricity tariffs for private households do not yet worthwhile from a financial point of view, since the investments by installing a smart meter still exceeding the cost savings effects (see WIK 2015)²⁴.

Variable electricity tariffs are a prerequisite for making other consumers, such as heat pumps and e-mobility, more flexible. Demand and generation management can be used to regulate the operating times of heat pump systems depending on storage conditions, heat demand and weather forecasts and, if necessary, to shift the heat generation in times of surplus of renewable electricity. Variable electricity tariffs can reduce heating costs for the end consumer and provide an incentive for providing control energy.

6 Options for electrical power marketing

6.1 Norway

In Norway applies the Pluskundeordningen (Plus consumer):

- The "plus consumer" – prosumer - both produces energy and uses electricity from the grid.
- The prosumer must have an agreement with the local grid operator. Excess energy can only be sold to an energy supplier.
- Limit of power at any given time: 100 kW. Normally the prosumer gets paid the Nordpool spot price for the excess energy delivered to the grid– average for 2019 was 0.05 €/kWh. Nordpool prices also depends on geographic location in Norway.
- The prosumer is exempted from paying certain tariffs, such as feed-in tariff.

6.2 France

In France two options for electrical power marketing are distinguished:

- Sale of all electricity
- Self-consumption and sale of surplus production

²³ Agora Energiewende (2017): New pricing models for energy: Basis for a reform of charges, taxes, levies and levies on electricity and fossil fuels. Berlin

²⁴ WIK Scientific Institute for Infrastructure and Communication Services GmbH (2015): Quantitative effects of variable electricity tariffs on household electricity costs. Short study for the consumer association of the Bundesverband e.V. (vzbv)

Sale of all electricity - 2020 prices

The customer installs photovoltaic panels and sells all its production at the rates reported in Table 19.

Table 19 Selling prices - All electricity option – kWp

Installation type	Power	Prices from 1/01 to 31/03/2020
Integrated in the envelope	≤ 3 kWp	18,53 ct/kWh
	≤ 9 kWp	15,35 ct/kWh
Non integrated	≤ 36 kWp	12,07 ct/kWh
	≤ 100 kWp	10,51 ct/kWh

These sales prices for photovoltaic electricity are valid from January 1st, 2020 to March 31st, 2020. This means that individuals who request connection to EDF during this period will benefit from these sales prices for photovoltaic electricity. This rate is valid until March 31st, 2020. EDF committing to buy electricity at this fixed rate for 20 years.

Sale of surplus electricity - 2020 prices

The investment premium and selling price for photovoltaic electricity (self-consumption with sale of surplus) are given in the Table 20 below.

Table 20 Selling prices - Surplus option

Power	Prices from 1/01 to 31/03/2020
≤ 3 kWp	Primus : 390 €/kWp/y and 10 ct/kWh
≤ 9 kWp	Primus : 290 €/kWp/y and 10 ct/kWh
≤ 36 kWp	Primus : 180 €/kWp/y and 6 ct/kWh
≤ 100 kWp	Primus : 90 €/kWp/y and 6 ct/kWh

Self-consumption with sale of surplus: the customer buys a photovoltaic generator for self-consumption, it consumes its production and sells the surplus to EDF if its production exceeds its consumption.

This premium decreases every quarter according to the volumes of connection requests and is paid over 5 years to the producer. It is set at:

- 390 €/kWp/year for an installation minor or equal to 3 kWp
- 290 €/kWp/year for an installation between 3 and 9 kWp

- 180 €/kWp/year for an installation between 9 and 36 kWp
- 90 € / kWp/year for an installation between 36 and 100 kWp

Electricity that will not be consumed instantly will be sold to EDF with a purchase obligation of 10 ct/kWh for installations less than or equal to 9 kWp and 6 ct/kWh for installations up to 100 kWp.

Two examples:

- For a photovoltaic installation of 3 kWp "the self-consumer" receives 1'170€/y (or 390€/kWp/y x 3 kWp) and he sells his surplus at 10 ct/kWh
- For a photovoltaic installation of 100 kWp "the self-consumer" receives 9'000€/y (or 90€/kWp/y x 100 kWp) and sells its surplus at 6 ct/kWh.

Energy metering

As explained before, it is possible to resell all or part of electrical production either to EDF or to another distribution company. The meter will calculate the amount of electricity produced and the price set by the distributor.

Figure 10 Energy metering

The meter is directly connected to the network and allows all energy production to be fed back into the network (Figure 10).

To determine the production of electricity, it is necessary to install two or three different meters:

- The energy meter is a classic meter found in all homes. It must be placed after the inverter and calculates the consumption of the home.
- The sales counter and the non-consumption counter can sometimes form one. The first is the tool that determines the amount of electricity produced by photovoltaic solar panels. It also notes the electricity injected into the network. It

can be placed before or after the purchase counter. The second ensures the supplier that the electricity produced is not illegally consumed by the producer.

When individuals want to consume the energy produced by their photovoltaic solar panels, they have the option of reselling only the surplus of electricity after consumption. In this case, two counters are needed. The first meter is installed after the solar inverter. It calculates the energy produced by photovoltaic solar panels. It is followed by the sales counter which determines the amount of electricity not consumed and injected into the network. There is also a single counter there to combine the tasks. The advantage is that this system is less expensive to install but, although more ecological, it is less profitable because only the surplus is bought back.

6.3 Germany

In Germany there are mainly three options: a) self-supply, b) direct delivery and c) fed-in of surplus (Figure 11).

Figure 11 Options for electrical power marketing of photovoltaics in Germany.

a) Self-supply: Consumption of produced power by same legal entity that operates the Photovoltaic system

- Identity of persons, no network transmission

Consequences for self-consumed electricity:

- No payment of network charges, CHP levy, concession fees
- Electricity tax exemption
- Obligation to pay a proportionate share of the EEG levy

b) Direct delivery: Supply via a direct line to a customer who is not the operator of the installation

- no identity of persons, without use of public network and in close proximity to each other on the same property (or building eg. tenants)

Consequences for electricity supplied:

- No payment of network charges, CHP levy, concession fees
- Electricity tax exemption
- Obligation to pay the EEG levy

Figure 12 Composition of price for electrical power in Germany depending on business case

Table 21 Composition of price for electrical power depending on business case

electricity purchased:		self-supply:		direct delivery	
Price components	[ct/kWh]	Price components	[ct/kWh]	Price components	[ct/kWh]
Energy price	x	Energy price	x	Energy price	x
network charges	6,43	network charges	-	network charges	-
electricity tax	2,05	electricity tax	-	electricity tax	-
EEG levy	6,76	EEG levy	2,70	EEG levy	6,76
CHP levy	0,28	CHP levy	-	CHP levy	-
§19 levy	0,31	§19 levy	-	§19 levy	-
offshore grid allocation	0,42	offshore grid allocation	-	offshore grid allocation	-
Allocation for switchable loads	0,01	Allocation for switchable loads	-	Allocation for switchable loads	-
concession levy	0,11	concession levy	-	concession levy	-
Distribution, Billing & Profit	x	Distribution, Billing & Profit	x	Distribution, Billing & Profit	x
Total netto*	24,35	Total netto	Σ x + 2,70	Total netto	Σ x + 6,76
VAT (19 %)	4,63	VAT (19 %)	Σ x + 0,51	VAT (19 %)	Σ x + 1,28
Total brutto	28,98	Total brutto	Σ x + 3,22	Total brutto	Σ x + 8,04

*Σ x = 8 ct/kWh

information:

- = Price component is omitted
x = variable value

c) surplus of produced electricity by photovoltaics which is not used directly onsite is fed into the public grid.

The remuneration according to **Renewable Energy Law (EEG)** depends on size and commissioning date of the plant and is reduced monthly according to national plan (Table 22).

Table 22 Remuneration for grid feed in of PV plants according to EEG

	EEG remuneration for grid feed of photovoltaic plants				
	0-10 kWp [ct/kWh]	10-40 kWp [ct/kWh]	40-100 kWp [ct/kWh]	100-750 kWp [ct/kWh]	other plants [ct/kWh]
Mrz 2020	10,42	10,14	8,06	8,06	7,31
Apr 2020	10,42	10,14	8,06	8,06	7,31
Mai 2020	10,40	10,12	8,04	8,04	7,29
Jun 2020	10,37	10,09	8,02	8,02	7,28
Jul 2020	10,34	10,07	8,00	8,00	7,26
Aug 2020	10,24	9,97	7,92	7,92	7,19
Sep 2020	10,14	9,87	7,84	7,84	7,11
Okt 2020	10,04	9,77	7,76	7,76	7,04
Nov 2020	9,94	9,67	7,68	7,68	6,97
Dez 2020	9,84	9,57	7,60	7,60	6,90
Jan 2021	9,74	9,48	7,53	7,53	6,83
Feb 2021	9,64	9,38	7,45	7,45	6,76
Mrz 2021	9,55	9,29	7,38	7,38	6,70

6.4 Italy

In Italy there are mainly two options for consumers: a) dedicated withdrawal, b) on-site exchange.

Dedicated withdrawal

The energy produced is sold to the GSE (Energy Services Manager, an Italian joint-stock company, entirely controlled by the Ministry of Economy and Finance) to whom the task of selling it is entrusted. It represents a simplified form of selling electricity to the grid.

Dedicated withdrawal is a service for the marketing of electricity produced and fed into the network as an alternative option to free market. Throughout the Dedicated withdrawal, electric energy fed into the grid by the plants is transferred to the GSE. It represents a simplified method available to producers of electricity from renewable sources (and not only those) to place electricity on the market, as an alternative to bilateral contracts or direct sale on the Stock Exchange. Energy is sold by the GSE on behalf of the producer. The GSE corresponds to the transferring producer a corresponding amount for each kWh placed on the network according to market economic conditions (C1).

Figure 13 Dedicated withdrawal scheme, Italy.

On-site exchange

In cases where there is energy produced by a system up to 500 kW and the plant is associated to an energy consumption center, on-site exchange can be activated. It is an incentive mechanism for the energy produced that allows the electricity grid to be used as a virtual storage of the electricity that is produced but not contextually self-consumed, so that it can be used later to satisfy your own electricity consumption. A necessary condition for the provision of the service is therefore the presence of plants for the consumption and production of electricity, underlying a single connection point with the public network.

At the same time, energy withdrawn from the grid is paid (Traditional electricity bill) to the operator at market conditions on the base of the contract.

The **Exchange on site mechanism** and the **traditional EE consumption bill** are managed by different entities, who operate on parallel tracks.

Normal withdrawal from the network: **Electricity bill.**

The consumption bill of EE (bimonthly for domestic customers) continues to be managed by the old distributor. The household will have a lower bill thanks to the saving on energy not consumed (produced and simultaneously self-consumed) and therefore not supplied by the network.

The on-site exchange mechanism is regulated on an economic basis by the GSE and managed with two annual down payments and an annual balance (payment, C2).

Two components (fractions) of energy are considered:

a) The energy exchanged with the network (put-in and picked-up):

- the electricity produced (and put-in) into the grid at a certain time,
- the energy picked-up at a time different from that in which the production takes place.

The energy exchanged is as a whole (with defined rules) valued through a contribution called "Contribution in exchange account". The determination of the value of the "Contribution in exchange account" is variable. It depends on the current market prices and the actual quantities of energy fed into and withdrawn from the network.

b) The energy produced by the system in surplus compared to the user's consumption is:

- credited for exchange grants for subsequent years,

- liquidated (paid) by the GSE; in this case, for tax purposes, the monetary settlement is configured as a sale and therefore the excess EE produced is remunerated by the GSE at market economic conditions (average market price - average PUN - of the previous year, defined by GME) in a single solution at the end of the year through a deposit into your bank account.

Each year the user has the option to choose for monetary settlement or for credit.

Figure 14 On-site exchange system in Italy.

Figure 15 A "traditional" situation (without Exchange on site).

PERSO = LOST ENERGY, ACQUISTATO= PURCHASED ENERGY, USCITA SOLARE= PV PRODUCTION, DOMANDA= ENERGY DEMAND

Figure 16 The target-situation of the mechanism (with Exchange on site).

SCAMBIO SUL POSTO = EXCHANGE ON SITE

Currently, in Italy the most convenient solution for those who produce less energy than consumed is “on-site exchange” with a storage battery and for those who produce more energy than consumed, the “dedicated withdrawal” is more suitable.

In the near future, the best solution for the enhancement of energy produced from renewables will be achieved by creating “Energy Communities” (Dir. 2001/2018/UE) that are local networks of people who exchange (even accumulating) green energy at subsidized and agreed prices.

6.5 Summary and Conclusion

All the four demo case countries offer remunerations for surplus photovoltaic energy fed into the public grid. The remunerations for Norway, France and Germany are limited up to photovoltaic plants with an installed power of 100 kW. Italian models of remunerations differ from the other countries as they offer the possibility of feeding surplus energy into the grid and use it later on site, as exchanged energy.

Figure 17 Remuneration for photovoltaic energy fed into the public grid

The remunerations for photovoltaic energy fed into the public grid are important to lower the high carbon emissions of Germans energy mix, see chapter 8. In France, due to nuclear power production, and in Norway, due to hydrogen power, the CO₂ emissions related to electricity production are already very low.

Only in Germany significant fees like the EEG-levy must be paid for self-consumption of produced energy from photovoltaic onsite. The resulting economic disadvantages from the EEG levy prevent the implementation of systems for the use of own electricity in multi-family buildings and neighbourhoods in large areas in Germany. The sector coupling between power, heat and mobility is important for achieving the climate protection goals. The existing EEG-levy represents barriers when implementing measures such as Power2Gas, storage systems or the integration of e-mobility. When renewable "excess electricity" is obtained from the public grid for electrolysis, the EEG levy currently has to be paid. The withdrawal of electricity from electricity storage facilities is partly treated like electricity from the grid, and it is also covered by the EEG levy. A financial disadvantage arises from the additional offer through the provision of storage capacity which contributes to network relief and flexibility. Another obstacle to the implementation of such projects is the elimination of the trade tax exemption for the housing industry, when is the case that it acts as an energy supplier. The EEG levy as an instrument to finance the energy transition needs to be reconsidered. Instead of taxing renewable energies, the consumption of fossil fuels should be charged. A gradual

reduction of the EEG levy, while increasing the CO₂ pricing for fossil fuels, would be the right signal.²⁵

Self-consumption is struggling to assert itself in France. According to RTE (Electricity Transport Network), only 20'000 French households had adopted this model in 2017, compared to 500'000 German households. We can mention the following measures to go beyond the brakes:

- Structure the industry with labels
- Simplify administrative procedures

Also, in the future, a likely increase in electricity prices may improve competitiveness and investment payback.

7 Practical example

Using a multifamily building as a fictive example, the impact of the different conditions of the four demo case countries on energy costs for household are compared. The fictive multifamily building has 15 dwellings and an electrical annual consumption of 2'500 kWh for each household. A 30 kWp photovoltaic plant with east/west orientation and 10° inclination is installed on the roof.

Figure 18 Practical example multifamily building

²⁵ Reduction of EEG-levy according to Prognos, EWI, GWS (2014), CO₂ pricing according to UBA (2013): Estimation of environmental costs in the areas of energy and transport, recommendations of the Federal Environment Agency, Germany, August 2013

The energy production in the CULTURAL-E demo case cities (Oslo, Bordeaux, Eisingen and Bologna), was estimated with the PV Performance Tool of PVGIS²⁶. Figure 19 shows the specific energy production of the 30 kWp photovoltaic plant which varies for each location from 697 kWh/kWp up to 1'076 kWh/kWp. For all countries, it is generally assumed that 30 % of the produced energy from the photovoltaic plant is used directly onsite and the resting surplus energy is fed into grid as surplus energy.

Figure 19 PV Energy production and use of the example building in each country

Energy costs for households depend on two factors: (i) the price for electricity from the grid and (ii) the price for the self-consumed energy from the photovoltaic plant. This price depends on the “PV electricity generation cost”. If necessary, additional cost for administration, measurement or taxes may be considered, considering that they could increase the costs for the self-consumed photovoltaic energy for households. The “PV electricity generation costs” are based on a general assumption for all countries of a PV costs of 1'200 €/kWp, a rate of interest of 2 %, a 1%/y maintenance per year and a technical lifespan of 25 years. Individual funding or tax reductions per country concerning the purchase of the PV plants are also considered. In Norway (25 %) and France (10 - 20 %) full VAT rates have to be paid for photovoltaic plants whereas in Italy (4%) and Germany (0%) VAT rates are reduced. However, France offers a funding for photovoltaic plants in the amount of 180 €/kWp/y for the duration of 5 years. This framework conditions lead to different costs for energy from photovoltaic plants. Whereas the costs in Norway, with 12.7 ct€/kWh, are the highest; in France, they are only 3.8 ct€/kWh; differently, in Italy and Germany, the cost is around 7.1 – 8.5 ct€/kWh (see dark blue column in Figure 20). For self-consumption of the produced energy on

²⁶ https://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvg_tools/en/tools.html#PVP

site in Italy and Germany, additional fees have to be paid. In Italy, additional administrative cost for self-consumption of 2.70 € per household and year are accounted, for which the increase of the cost is not significant. For self-consumed energy in Germany, EEG levy and administrative costs for accounting and distribution has to be paid, which leads to a significant increase of costs for households; it varies from 8.5 ct€/kWh up to 19.6 ct€/kWh for the self-consumed electric energy from the photovoltaic plant on side (see light blue column in Figure 20). The difference between the costs for electricity from grid (yellow column) and the cost for self-consumed energy is decisive for the profitability of a PV system with a high share of self-consumption. In France, Germany and Italy, around 9 - 17 ct€/kWh can be saved with self-consumption. Combined with a secured feed-in tariff or a corresponding other model for the remuneration of surplus energy, photovoltaic systems on the building roof are economically accessible. In Norway, the PV electricity costs (around 12.7 ct€/kWh) are slightly higher than electricity from grid.

Figure 20 Energy costs for households in multifamily building

Taking into account the differences in costs for electricity from the grid and the costs for self-consumed photovoltaic energy, the monthly costs for households range from 25 - 27 € in Norway, France and Italy; whereas, households in Germany have by far the highest cost for electricity with monthly costs over 56 €. The model “on site exchange” in Italy is funding the exchange of energy, which means that (i) the surplus energy from the photovoltaic system can be used on site afterwards and (ii) the cost for electricity from grid is reduced taking into account the corresponding amount.

Figure 21 Resulting monthly costs for electricity per household

8 Environmental Data

The composition of electricity production in Norway, France, Germany and Italy is shown in Figure 22 and Figure 23.

Figure 22 Electricity production in Norway²⁷ (left) and France²⁸ (right)

²⁷ national electricity disclosure 2018 from The Norwegian Energy Regulatory Authority; <https://www.nve.no/norwegian-energy-regulatory-authority/retail-market/electricity-disclosure-2018/>

²⁸ The National transmission system operator RTE (Electricity Transmission Network)

Figure 23 Electricity production in Germany²⁹ (left) and Italy³⁰ (right)

The Global Warming potential (GWP) or CO₂ equivalent of power from the public grid shows the environmental impact of the electricity production in the respective country (Figure 24).

Figure 24 GWP for electricity from grid in 2020

The GIS based “electricityMap”³¹ visualises climate-relevant emissions from actual power generation and power consumption in Europe (Figure 25).

²⁹ <https://strom-report.de/strom/#strommix-2019-deutschland>

³⁰ https://www.climate-transparency.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/B2G_2019_Italy.pdf

³¹ <https://www.electricitymap.org/?page=map&solar=false&remote=true&wind=false>

Figure 25 GWP of electricity from Grid in Europe, electricity map.org

9 General Conclusion

Each country has its own building regulations with criteria for building insulation, efficiency of system technologies and share of renewable energy supply. Going in detail, the regulations differ remarkably and are not comparable. Norway and France have fixed values for the limit of useful, final or primary energy demand. Germany and Italy use the building reference method without a fixed value. **None of the four CULTURAL-E partner countries assesses the effective greenhouse gas emissions of building energy concepts. None of the building regulations considers the entire energy demand on site during the complete life cycle including the user appliances and the embodied energy for building construction.** The legal minimum requirements have strong disparities; hence it implies variations in regard to achievable GWP reductions. Except for Norway (ban on fossil fuels for heat supply and a largely renewable electricity mix) the minimum requirements for nZEB are behind the PEB standard.

Nevertheless, it exists several incentives for promoting PEB using innovative energy concepts beyond the existing minimum legal requirements. **In all the four countries there are numerous funding programs for measures** such as building standards, heating systems based on renewable energies, insulation of the building envelope,

photovoltaic systems or e-mobility. Furthermore, some countries offer a partial VAT reduction for the investment in PV systems. So far, there are no funding schemes for alternative construction methods, although a lightweight or hybrid construction causes far lower CO₂ emissions than a solid construction in reinforced concrete or masonry.

Whereas the electricity prices in Norway and France are comparatively low, the households in Italy and Germany have to pay double the price. The reasons are the high taxes in Germany, including the EEG-levy and high charges for network and energy & distribution in Italy. Variable pricing options depending on time are offered in France and Italy. In France for example the variable pricing option is linked with the nuclear power production. By offering a low off-peak rate for 8 hours a day, the power consumption can be postponed and thus can help the French energy system to better manage the peak of consumption. In Italy, the intention to offer variable rates is to benefit those who consume energy not at peak times. Variable energy prices as an instrument to make better use of renewables, with tariffs that calculate the electricity costs from the current electricity prices and thus take into account the strong fluctuation of the energy provided by wind and solar systems within one day, does not exist yet.

All the four demo case countries offer remunerations for surplus photovoltaic energy fed into the public grid. The remunerations for Norway, France and Germany are limited up to photovoltaic systems with an installed power of 100 kW. Italian models of remunerations differ from the other countries as they offer the possibility of feeding surplus energy into the grid and use it later on site as exchanged energy. Self-consumption of produced energy from photovoltaic plants on site is possible in each country. Particularly in Germany self-consumed electricity from PV on site is combined with high levies and costs for administrative procedures for measurement and billing.

In addition, the overarching energy infrastructure affects the CO₂ emissions of buildings. The boundary conditions coming from the energy mix in each country differ a lot. Norway with electricity generated from hydrogen power plants (18 gCO_{2e} per kWh) and France with mostly nuclear power (60 gCO_{2e} per kWh) have the lowest emissions for electricity from grid, whereas these emissions in Germany (440 gCO_{2e} per kWh) with still 40 % of fossil energy sources and partly nuclear power and Italy (312 gCO_{2e} per kWh) with 60 % of fossil energy sources are higher.

Outlook and recommendations

To achieve a real steering effect, a fixed CO₂ target value for buildings has to be set instead of maintaining the previous assessment of reference buildings and primary energy requirement. There exists a large number of subsidies' models for energy efficient buildings and renewable energies, but not always they are made use of and neither the effectiveness of the measures are transparent in regard to CO₂ savings or they are proven to be enough. **Future funding programs should subsidize energy**

concepts for CO₂-saving, such as PEB design criteria instead of individual and isolated measures. Or there may be an obligation to pay taxes when targets according to the ‘individual climate protection plans’ of the building are not met; or, a subsidisation of monitored CO₂ savings, when they are already achieved beyond the foreseen targets.

The CO₂ emissions’ pricing of energy sources across all sectors, including the fossil fuels used for heat and transport, is an effective measure as well. In Germany, there is a starting of CO₂ pricing with 25 € per tonCO₂ by 2021³². In order to develop a real steering effect in reducing the greenhouse potential and the spread of PEB concepts, the CO₂ costs must be set up to 180 € per tonCO₂, including an increase up to 240 € per tonCO₂ by 2050 (UBA 2013)³³.

Another objective of PEB design is to reduce the environmental impact in the entire life cycle of a building. Therefore, **the boundaries for the building assessment has to be expanded by the proportion of the embodied energy for building construction and the energy requirement for building operation, including the user appliances.** A future CO₂ target value for residential buildings must consider these boundaries to further expand the use of self-generated electricity from locally generated PV power and thus to support the spread of PEB design concepts. In order to promoting sector coupling of energy demand in building, it is sensible to assess the energy demand of e-mobility in the medium term.

For the envisioned coupling of the electricity, heating and mobility sectors, it is a crucial aspect **to consider the introduction of district level approaches compared to an individual assessment of buildings.** By implementing energy systems at district level, which includes the generation and storage of renewable energy systems, as well as the provision of local heat and electricity for buildings and mobility, CO₂ savings can be achieved that go beyond the individual building approach. A district level approach also makes other important aspects possible, such as energy storage and flexibility for energy demand and generation, and thus contribute to the grid stabilization.

Variable electricity tariffs are a prerequisite for making other measures, such as heat pumps and e-mobility, more flexible. Demand and generation management can be used to regulate the operating times of heat pump systems depending on storage conditions, heat demand and weather forecasts and, if necessary, to shift the heat generation in times of surplus of renewable electricity. **Variable electricity tariffs can reduce heating costs for the end consumer and provide an incentive for providing control energy.**

³² Klimaschutzplan 2030

³³ Estimation of environmental costs in the areas of energy and transport, recommendations of the Federal Environment Agency, Germany, August 2013